

HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF PARALINGUISTICS.

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ABSTRACT: To date, we can see that a lot of research has been done in history of paralinguistics. Significant work has also been done on paralinguistics, which is an important branch of science. This article analyzes research related to paralinguistics from a historical perspective. The aim is to study the work of researchers and the peculiarities of the historical formation of paralinguistics.

KEYWORDS: canonical, paralinguistics, German Vemberi, psycholinguistics or metalinguistics, Treger and Smith, culture, ethnography, ethics, anthropology, religion, and customs.

Concepts of paralinguistic tools were first studied in England in 1644 in D. Bulwer's work entitled "The Natural Language and Chronology of the Hand Expressing Speech and Communicating Gestures". On the basis of his scientific theory, in the period between 1650 and 1670, researchers and researchers such as I. Shlezinger, L. Namir, R. Berdvistel, E. Klim, U. Stokoe, and U. Belludji published scientific works on paralinguistic tools. In their scientific work, the researchers conducted research on the systematization, regulation and creation of a single explanatory dictionary that represents the essence of gestures. Research works on paralinguistics as phonetic phenomena were carried out in 1930 by N. It was also studied by Yushmanov in his work "Unnatural Phonetics". According to scientists, abnormal phonetic phenomena in paralinguistic means also include specific types of canonical sounds and sound combinations formed in speech. Elements of unusual phonetics can be used as an expressive-descriptive tool in artistic speech, for example, describing the singing of birds, etc[1].

Nevertheless, paralinguistic tools were first studied within the framework of linguistics in the early 1950s in the United States in connection with the cultural sciences of psychology, ethnography, medicine, and anthropology. In particular, its origin was founded in 1940 by American linguist A. Hill (USA), and its independent development as a science dates back to 1960.

In the 70s and 80s of the 20th century, paralinguistic tools were first considered as a psychological speech process, and then as a secondary component of verbal communication in linguistics. These theoretical ideas and ideas have remained almost unchanged to this day, and paralinguistic tools are still being studied as a means of secondary communication.

In modern linguistics, Paralinguistics as a practical science is studied in the process of speech communication at Oxford University, and it is given great importance in various psychological trainings.

In modern encyclopedic dictionaries, 3 types of paralinguistic tools are noted:

- a) phonation (tempo, volume, pronunciation of sounds, speed of conversation, various pauses);
- b) kinesics (gestures, facial expressions, holding the body part in different poses);
- c) graphics (use or addition of various conventional symbols instead of letters, changes in font and font size).

In modern linguistics, a new step has been taken in the field of comprehensive study by connecting paralinguistic tools to various fields. Especially in recent years, attention has been paid to the study of non-verbal means in social, concrete and natural sciences. It can be said that until people fully began to communicate through the verbal path, the main means of communication were now the components that included paralinguistics. Due to similar factors, it can be said that this branch of linguistics appeared earlier than other branches. There is some research on the study of paralinguistic tools in different languages. Although relatively old, the field of paralinguistics cannot be said to have been fully studied so far. In the scientific research of modern linguistics, we can witness that paralinguistics studies issues related to gesture, facial expression, and sound quality[2]. This field is one of the most relevant areas of linguistics today. Although much work has been done, a comparative typological study of paralinguistic tools has been virtually unexplored. In this article, we aim to analyze the views expressed on these same issues. The ideas expressed by the participants of the speech should have their own impact, attractiveness, demand for observation. Paralinguistics, with its main aspects mentioned above, serves to give speech a special significance, as well as to create imagery in speech. In particular, Professor A. Nurmonov gives the following information. "German Vemberi was a well-known orientalist who knew not only the Arabic, Persian, and Uzbek languages, but also the culture and customs of these peoples. It is not felt at all. As a scholar of Islam, the history and culture of the peoples of the East, he is respected among the population. But in one sitting, impressed by the very pleasant music, he involuntarily begins to shake his leg at the rhythm of the melody. This move reveals to the circle that he is a foreigner. For among the peoples of the East, melody was a sign of

enjoyment of singing, not by the movement of the feet, but by the gradual oscillation of the head in a horizontal position." [4] Thus, the integral connection of paralinguistic means with culture, ethnography, ethics, anthropology, religion, and customs finds its own expression in each language. Research in this area is of great importance.

Contemplating the importance of paralinguistics today and paralinguistic research is not considered a complex issue. Initial researches were by American linguists, J. L. Trager and G. L. Smith. But the work done and the materials prepared by them have become more vague than they are now and in the recent past. Subsequently, a number of purposeful and well-thought-out actions were taken to generalize the basis of the field. In 1962, a comprehensive conference was held at Indiana University. The main purpose of the conference was a more in-depth study of paralinguistics. Later, D. G. Mouton's book, *An Approach to Semiotics*, also played a major role in the study of paralinguistics. The conference, organized by Indiana University, is of great importance. For example, this large event brought together very scattered materials that were considered by Trager and Smith to be industry stimulants. Although they cited a great deal of information, almost all of the sources were cited by them in their books written in different years. The work carried out by Trager and Smith helped to clearly define the general principles on which many programs are based, while a number of promising research directions were proposed and, in some sections, very specific research topics were identified. [3] In this way, the conference participants presented a large amount of information and created a complete picture of the period of the science of paralinguistics up to 1960. It should be noted that many of the researches conducted in recent years are directly related to this conference and the work of Trager and Smith.

There are different views on the study of paralinguistics. One of the main problems here is related to the review of the research conducted. British linguist, academician D. Crystal raises the following important issues in the study of paralinguistics in the sixties: The further development of the approach described mainly by Trager and the expansion of its scope in other, non-linguistic fields; work on the features of paralinguistics that Trager and Smith did not study; clearly define the object and function of the study of this field. The term paralinguistics was first introduced to science by A. Hill. Later, Traiger and Smith wrote a work in this field, defining the subject, the task, the essence of the phenomena studied. But they did not say that parathyroidism plays a different role in every nation. In this case, the field is studied only on the basis of

structural linguistics. Similar factors have caused a number of confusions. Part of the reason for the confusion associated with the study of paralinguistics today is, of course, related to how linguistics developed in the sixties. Preliminary definitions of paralinguistics were made only within the theoretical and descriptive framework provided by Trager and Smith. Professor of Linguistics and Anthropology at the University of Florida, N.Y. Merkel will comment on Trager at the Indiana conference. "If we look at the research, we can see that everything we want to call paralinguistics is covered by Trager. Also, what we don't cover is not considered paralinguistics, they are psycholinguistics or metalinguistics." [3]

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